

REVIEW

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TED (Turtle Evolution Database), an online database of fossil turtles from Czechia and Poland with images and 3D models

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Abstract

The Turtle Evolution Database (TED) is an online database initially dedicated to fossil turtles from Czechia and Poland, featuring images and 3D models. This database aims to provide comprehensive information about fossil specimens, including their locations, ages, taxonomic identification, and related references. TED adopts the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) to enhance global collaboration and accessibility to lesser-known paleontological collections. TED currently includes over 250 records from 17 institutions, covering nine families of turtles and other related material. The database is freely accessible under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International license, promoting responsible use and broad sharing of data. Researchers worldwide are encouraged to contribute, provide feedback, and collaborate to further the understanding of turtle evolution. The database is available at <https://ted.paleo.pan.pl/>.

Introduction

In the modern world, a key aspect of the research is the easy access to information. The tempo of research pushes paleontologists and other researchers to immediate results and the time for proper investigations in collections abroad, non-English literature reviews, or writing extensive monographs is limited. One of the powerful tools is online databases cumulating and providing access to information. Currently, several extant and extinct biodiversity-focused databases exist (e.g., PBDB, GBIF, Mindat, and iDigBio). All of them are different, but generally are mostly designed with recording of spatial or spatiotemporal occurrences of taxa in mind, usually either at a specific or collection level, and either do not provide

granular, specimen-level information, or their capabilities in that regard are limited. Besides the information about occurrence locations of fossil species with maps, ages, and a brief description of the material with its taxonomic identification and related references, we aim to provide pictures of individual specimens and, whenever possible, 3D models. With the adoption of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, the main idea is to open smaller, not well-known or difficult to access collections to other researchers, allow recognition of the nature of preserved material, and extend global collaboration. In the current project, we started with material from two Central European countries, namely Czechia and Poland. Much of the historical fossil turtle material from these countries has not been described, documented, or revised in English-language literature since its discovery, and therefore, both countries represent a blank spot on the biogeographic map, despite a relatively rich and diverse fossil record. We reviewed the current knowledge about fossil turtles from Czechia and Poland and present an online database to you. Researchers worldwide are most welcome to contribute, give us feedback, and most of all, collaborate with us to reveal

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the fascinating turtle evolution. The database is available under the link <https://ted.paleo.pan.pl/>.

Review of Czech and polish fossil turtles

The fossil record of turtles from Czechia and Poland (Fig. 1) is extensive temporarily (Triassic until Recent), taxonomically (stem turtles and a wide range of cryptodires), and historically; the earliest note of turtle fossils from Poland (now unfortunately lost) is as early as 1816, based on the catalogue of the Department of Mineralogy of the Jagiellonian University in Cracow (pers. comm., Piotr Kajdas). The oldest description of a fossil turtle from Czechia was provided by Reuss (1855, p. 78), a shell of a sea turtle NMP Ob 00006 (Protostegidae or Dermochelyidae) from Slavětín-Pátek (Bílá Hora Formation), dated to the Early Turonian (Kear et al., 2014). Slightly younger, the second historically oldest mention of fossil turtle is provided by Jokély (1858, p. 534) from the locality Vintřov close to Radonice (Most Formation), dated to Early Miocene (Burdigalian), currently lost.

From stratigraphic point of view, Late Triassic (Norian) deposits of Poland (Poreba, Kierszula, and Kocury fossil sites: Czepiński et al., 2021; Sulej et al., 2012) yielded hundreds of specimens, including several almost complete shells, girdles, and limbs of *Proterochersis porebensis*, which is one of the oldest and least derived testudinans (e.g., Szczygielski, 2017; Szczygielski & Piechowski, 2023; Szczygielski & Sulej, 2016, 2019). The Jurassic turtle material from Poland is more fragmentary and includes a pancryptodiran turtle *Owadonia borsukbiałynicka*, a plesiochelyid cf. *Craspedochelys* sp. (Borsuk-Białynicka & Młynarski, 1968; Madzia et al., 2021; Szczygielski et al., 2018), and indeterminate turtle specimens (Dames, 1888; Deecke, 1907). The former species has a durophagy-suggesting morphology of the mandible, divergent from that observed in other Jurassic taxa and more resembling that of modern-day sea turtles. Cretaceous deposits are more represented across the Czech-Polish borderlands, where a protostegid sea turtle specimen from Milovice (CZ), originally described as *Iserosaurus litoralis*, contains several postcranial long bones and shell fragments (Frič, 1910; Frič & Bayer, 1905; Kear et al., 2014). Also, more sea turtles are known from the Bohemian Cretaceous Basin, however, they lack more characters allowing precise taxonomic attribution and generally are referable to Chelonioida indet., however, usually resembling protostegid turtles (Frič & Bayer, 1905; Kear et al., 2014; Laube, 1885). A similar situation appears to involve protostegid sea turtles from the Annapol fossil site of Poland (Kapuścińska & Machalski, 2015), although the material in question is more diagnostic and may warrant establishment of new taxa (in preparation). The same is true for the material from the Pecínov locality (CZ), which

is still under preparation. Nevertheless, all those findings are important in the context of the biodiversity in the Central European area. The richest and most investigated stratigraphic interval is the Cenozoic. The first one is the Eocene record from the locality Kučlín (CZ), probably an isolated fragment of costal of trionyhid turtle (mentioned as *Trionyx* sp.), however, this record has never been figured or more described and exists only as a piece of information in the literature (Kafka, 1911; Laube, 1882). The Oligocene fossil record is represented by the sea turtle *Glarichelys* aff. *knorri* from Menilite Shales of Winnica (PL), Litenčice (CZ), and Hermanowa (PL) (Młynarski, 1959a; Gregorová & Młynarski, 1992; Příkrýl et al., 2016). In this environmental group we also include the record of an indeterminate femur of Pan-Cheloniidae from Kienberg, yet the find is younger, from the Miocene of the Vienna Basin (Březina et al., 2024). The second assemblage consists of semi-aquatic species of the Polish Miocene, represented by a group of freshwater and terrestrial turtles including genera *Chelydropsis*, *Geoemyda*, *Ptychogaster*, and *Testudo* from the Opole and Przeworno fossil sites (Młynarski, 1978, 1981a, b, 1984a, b; Wegner, 1913).

The Miocene fossil record is rich, especially from the Eger Graben fossil sites in NW Bohemia. At least six different turtle genera were observed from the Most Basin, namely *Testudo*, *Rafetus*, *Ptychogaster*, *Clemmydopsis*, *Chelydropsis*, and *Manouria morla*, and that makes the NW Bohemia a hotspot of turtle diversity during the Burdigalian (Chroust et al., 2023, 2025; Dvořák et al., 2010; Kvaček et al., 2004). We would like to highlight the large number of fossil trionyhid specimens attributed to *Rafetus bohemicus*. Material from Ahníkov is currently under our work. From neighbouring basins, turtle material from the Cheb Basin is identified as the genera *Ptychogaster* and *Testudo* (Frič, 1893; Młynarski & Roček, 1985), whereas material from the Zittau Basin is identified as Testudinoidea indet. (Brachaniec et al., 2022). From south Bohemia, two fossil sites Strakonice and Bohunice, provided turtle material as well, generally undiagnostic in lower taxonomic ranks, however, specimens of *Ptychogaster* sp. from Strakonice were recognised (Dašková et al., 2017; Procházka, 1929). From the Moravian region, turtle material encompasses three different turtle genera from Brno and the Mokrá-Quarry: *Ptychogaster*, *Testudo*, and *Titanochelon* (Březina et al., 2019; Luján et al., 2021). From Hodonín, remains of trionyhids and testudinids are under description. The third group represents terrestrial and semi-aquatic environments, where at least three different turtle genera (*Emys*, *Geoemyda*, and *Testudo*) are known from the Pliocene fossil sites of Działoszyn, Węże, Rębielice Królewskie, and Zalesiaki

(Młynarski, 1955, 1956, 1959b, 1964a). The Pleistocene turtle remains are limited only to the genus *Emys* from Přezletice and Koněprusy fossil sites (Młynarski, 1964b; Zázvorka, 1938, 1957). Younger Holocene remains from Czech archeological sites are well listed in Široký et al. (2004), whereas the Polish (sub)fossil material is known from Legnica, Kamień Mały, and Racibórz (personal observation). Foreign material is rare in the Czech and Polish collections, however, we discovered in Czech and Polish collections an unlabelled shell of *Pleurosternon* sp. from the UK, a carapace of *Eusarkia rotundiformis* from Tunisia, dozens of gypsum casts of *Trionyx vinodobensis* from Austria, locality Eibiswald, casts of *Paleomeodusa testa* from Kelheim, Germany and turtle material (*Emys orbicularis*, *Chelydropsis* sp.) from Slovakia, localities Hajnáčka and Ivanovce (Młynarski, 1963). Therefore, this material is included even though it is not from Czechia or Poland. Not all of the material listed in Table 1 is sufficiently prepared or identified to be published in TED at the moment, however, we want to give the reader an accurate impression about the material. More information will be gradually added with time.

The fossil record of turtles in Central Europe spans from the Triassic period to the (sub)recent era and is rich both in terms of time and taxonomy, including stem turtles as well as a diverse array of cryptodires. However, it is unevenly sampled and documented. Countries with a long, established history of paleontology, such as Germany and Switzerland, produced over centuries hundreds of contributions regarding their turtle material, resulting in its constant presence in the scientific discourse, whereas areas closer to the eastern flank, such as Czechia and Poland, tend to have a much more limited record, often restricted to local journals with a restricted outreach. As a result, hundreds of turtle specimens remain unpublished or only barely documented, and are unknown to the international public, and in some cases even to the local scientific community. Therefore, a set of problems can be identified:

1. The material is numerous, and its true richness (specimen-wise and taxonomical) is difficult to estimate. Much of the material was never published. As a result, without contacting or visiting the institutions, its presence is impossible to establish by external researchers. In some cases, even the collection curators are not aware of its existence in their collections or its true scientific value.
2. Some of the material was published historically (mostly in the twentieth century) only in local journals (that is, e.g., in Czech or Polish), which may now be discontinued or otherwise difficult to access

even in the countries of their origin. Functionally, in an international context, such material remains unknown, as if it was unpublished. If known, its current location or even existence may be unknown.

3. Even if relevant publications are reencountered, in many cases the documentation is subpar, with sparse, poor quality photographs or simplified, stylized drawings, and interpretations preserved by the original authors may be long outdated. When the documentation is poor or incomplete, only personal examination of the material may allow verification of its identity.
4. In many cases, the material is spread out between numerous smaller and larger scientific institutions and local museums, making it difficult for researchers to examine it.

Thanks to the current tools of data acquisition and sharing, most of those problems can be solved and the valuable natural history heritage may be easily introduced or reintroduced to the scientific community. The solution requires:

1. A comprehensive review of the available material, including unpublished specimens, and specimen-level acknowledgement of its existence.
2. A reference base, including records of historical literature with references to described specimens and confirmation of their existence and location.
3. A modern mode of documentation, including high quality photographs and 3D models, allowing researchers to recognize material which is relevant to them and which requires study. Because specialty of various researchers may pertain to, e.g., particular taxonomic units, time slices, geographic or environmental settings, or anatomical regions, all of those aspects must be easily searchable, and must include a robust system of cross-references.
4. Establishment of an easy and convenient connection between the material, its housing institutions, and specialists, sparking intensive research endeavors. To accomplish this, the data must be accessible, granular, accurate, and easy to navigate.

A review of current databases and the importance of a new database

This section's aim is to define our database against other current possibilities and not to extensively criticise them. It must be stressed that we appreciate the work of people behind them, but we note that TED's fossil turtle specimen-centered approach is currently not shared by any international database. The Paleobiology Database

Table 1 Turtle material from Czechia and Poland

Locality	Age	Taxa	Material	References
Poręba (PL)	Late Triassic: Norian	<i>Proterochersis porebensis</i>	Almost complete shells and shell fragments, appendicular bones, vertebrae, bromalites	Sulej et al. (2012), Szczygielski and Sulej (2016, 2019), Bajdek et al. (2019), Szczygielski and Piechowski (2023)
Kocury (PL)		<i>Proterochersis cf. porebensis</i>	Shell fragments, appendicular bones	Czepiński et al. (2021)
Kierszula (PL)		Testudinata indet	Shell fragments, appendicular bone	Work in progress
Czarnogłowy (PL)	Late Jurassic: Kimmeridgian	'Plesiochelyidae' indet	Shell fragments	Deecke (1907), Madzia et al. (2021)
Krzyżanowice (PL)		cf. <i>Craspedochelys</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Borsuk-Białynicka and Młynarski (1968), Madzia et al. (2021)
Wrzoso (PL)		Testudines indet	Shell fragments	Dames (1888), Madzia et al. (2021)
Owadów (PL)	Late Jurassic: Tithonian	<i>Owadovia borsukbiallynickae</i>	Mandible fragment, appendicular bones	Szczygielski et al. (2018)
Annopol (PL)	Early Cretaceous: Albian	Protostegidae indet	Shell fragments, cranial fragments, appendicular bones	Kapuścińska and Machalski (2015)
Pecínov (CZ)	Late Cretaceous: Cenomanian	Protostegidae indet	Shell fragments	Work in progress
Bílá Hora (CZ)	Late Cretaceous: Turonian	Dermochelyoidea indet	Skull endocast, appendicular bones	Frič and Bayer (1905), Kear et al. (2014)
Měcholupy (CZ)		<i>Pygmaeochelys michelobana</i>	Partial shell (lost)	Laube (1896a)
Milovice (CZ)		Protostegidae indet. (<i>Iserosaurus litoralis</i>)	Shell fragments, appendicular bones	Frič and Bayer (1905), Kear et al. (2014)
Slavětín-Pátek (CZ)		Dermochelyoidea indet	Partial shell	Reuss (1855), Kear et al. (2014)
Přibylův (CZ)		Chelonioidea indet	Isolated coracoid	Kear et al. (2014)
Kučlín (CZ)	Eocene: Priabonian	<i>Trionyx</i> sp.	Isolated costal (lost)	Laube (1882), Kafka (1911)
Dětaň (CZ)	Oligocene: Rupelian	Testudinidae indet	Shell fragments, appendicular bones	Fejfar (1987)
Hermanowa (PL)		<i>Glarichelys</i> aff. <i>knorri</i>	Almost complete specimen	Přikryl et al. (2016)
Litenčice (CZ)		cf. <i>Glarichelys</i> sp.	Disarticulated specimen	Gregorová and Młynarski (1992)
Winnica (PL)		<i>Glarichelys</i> aff. <i>knorri</i>	Almost complete specimen	Młynarski (1959a), Młynarski (1984b)
Valeč (CZ)		Testudinoidea indet	Shell fragments	Dvořák et al. (2010)
Ahňokov (CZ)	Miocene: Burdigalian	<i>Chelydropsis</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Dvořák et al. (2010)
		<i>Clemmydropsis</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Dvořák et al. (2010)
		<i>Manouria morla</i>	Shell fragments	Chroust et al. (2025)
		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Several articulated/disarticulated shells	Dvořák et al. (2010)
		<i>Testudo</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Dvořák et al. (2010)
		Trionychinae indet	Shell fragments	Dvořák et al. (2010)
Brno (CZ)		<i>Titanochelon</i> cf. <i>vitodurana</i>	Shell fragments, appendicular bones	Březina et al. (2019)
Břešťany (CZ)		<i>Chelydropsis</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Laube (1900), Laube (1901)
		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Shell fragments, appendicular bones	Liebus (1930)
		<i>Rafetus bohemicus</i>	Several articulated/disarticulated shells, appendicular bones, and skulls	Laube (1898), Laube (1900), Laube (1901), Liebus (1930), Chroust et al. (2023)
Hodonín (CZ)		<i>Testudo</i> sp.	Several articulated/disarticulated shells	Work in progress
		Trionychinae indet	Several articulated/disarticulated shells	Work in progress

Table 1 (continued)

Locality	Age	Taxa	Material	References
Komořany u Mostu (CZ)		<i>Rafetus bohemicus</i>	Partial shell	Hurník (1965)
Košťany (CZ)		<i>Rafetus bohemicus</i>	Partial shell	Dvořák et al. (2010)
Lom u Mostu (CZ)		<i>Rafetus bohemicus</i>	Partial shell	Laube (1895), Laube (1896b), Chroust et al. (2023)
Louka u Litvínova (CZ)		<i>Rafetus bohemicus</i>	Partial shell	Laube (1896b), Chroust et al. (2023)
Mokrá (CZ)		<i>Testudo</i> (<i>Chersine</i>) cf. <i>kalksburgensis</i>	Shell fragments	Luján et al. (2021)
		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Luján et al. (2021)
Skyřice (CZ)		<i>Chelydropsis</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Schlosser & Hibsich (1902), Laube (1910), Schlosser (1910)
		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Schlosser & Hibsich (1902), Laube (1910), Schlosser (1910)
Souš u Mostu (CZ)		<i>Rafetus bohemicus</i>	Partial shell	Hurník (1965)
Teplice (CZ)		<i>Rafetus bohemicus</i>	Shell fragments	Dvořák et al. (2010)
Tuchořice (CZ)		<i>Chelydropsis</i> sp.	Undetermined material	Dvořák et al. (2010)
		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Undetermined material	
		<i>Testudo</i> sp.	Undetermined material	
Turów (PL)		Testudinoidea indet	Shell fragment	Brachaniec et al. (2022)
Varvažov (CZ)		<i>Rafetus bohemicus</i>	Partial shell	Dvořák et al. (2010)
Vintřov (CZ)		Testudinoidea indet	Shell fragments (lost)	Jokély (1858)
Želeč (CZ)		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Laube (1901)
Bohunice (CZ)	Miocene: Langhian	Testudinoidea indet	Shell fragments, appendicular bone	Dašková et al. (2017)
Cheb? (CZ)		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp. (<i>Testudo calcarea</i>)	Isolated epiplastra	Frič (1893)
Dolnice (CZ)		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Several disarticulated shells	Młynarski and Roček (1985)
		<i>Testudo</i> sp.	Several disarticulated shells	Młynarski and Roček (1985)
Kienberg (CZ)		Cheloniidae indet	Proximal head of the left femur	Březina et al. (2024)
Strakonice (CZ)		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Procházka (1929)
Opole (PL)	Miocene: Serravalian	<i>Geoemyda eureia</i>	Almost complete shells (lost), shell fragments	Wegner (1913), Młynarski (1984a), Młynarski (1984b)
Przeworno (PL)		<i>Chelydropsis</i> sp.	Skull, shell fragments, appendicular bones	Młynarski (1978), Młynarski (1981a), Młynarski (1981b), Młynarski (1984a)
		' <i>Geoemyda</i> ' sp.	Shell fragments	Młynarski (1978), Młynarski (1984a)
		<i>Ptychogaster</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Młynarski (1978), Młynarski (1984a)
		<i>Testudo</i> sp.	Shell fragments	Młynarski (1978), Młynarski (1984a)
Węże (PL)	Pliocene: Zanclean	' <i>Geoemyda</i> ' <i>mossoczyi</i>	Shell fragments	Młynarski (1955), Młynarski (1984b)
		<i>Testudo szalarii</i>	Shell fragments	Młynarski (1955)
		<i>Emys orbicularis</i>	Shell fragments, appendicular bones	Młynarski (1955), Młynarski (1984b)
Zalesiaki (PL)		' <i>Geoemyda</i> ' <i>mossoczyi</i>	Shell fragments	Młynarski (1977), Młynarski (1978)
Rębielice Królewskie (PL)	Pliocene: Piacenzian	' <i>Geoemyda</i> ' <i>mossoczyi</i>	Shell fragments, appendicular bones	Młynarski (1959b), Młynarski (1964a, 1964b), Młynarski (1977), Młynarski (1984b)
		<i>Emys orbicularis</i>	Shell fragments, appendicular bones	Młynarski (1964a), Młynarski (1977), Młynarski (1984b)

Table 1 (continued)

Locality	Age	Taxa	Material	References
Koněprusy (CZ)	Pleistocene: Chibanian	<i>Emys orbicularis</i>	Shell fragments	Zázvorka (1957), Młynarski (1964b), Šíroký et al. (2004)
Přezletice (CZ)		<i>Emys orbicularis</i>	Shell fragments	Zázvorka (1938), Šíroký et al. (2004)
Legnica (PL)	Holocene: Northgrippian	<i>Emys orbicularis</i>	Shell mold	Undescribed
Kamień Mały (PL)	Holocene: Meghalayan	<i>Emys orbicularis</i>	Shell fragments	Undescribed
Racibórz (PL)		<i>Emys orbicularis</i>	Partial shell	Undescribed

(PBDB) is the most used tool for searching for information on fossil taxa. However, by principle, it is based nearly solely on published records, which restricts its utility as a source of information on undescribed (and thus, requiring scientific attention the most) material, whereas historical records, often outdated and inaccurate due to the limited state of knowledge at the time of original publication, subsequent improvements and changes to the systematic and phylogenetic framework, etc., can be misleading and are difficult to correct. Moreover, PBDB is designed to record occurrences of taxa in fossil localities, but it allows only rudimentary information on type material and provides no means for tracing individual specimens. PBDB does not support picture upload, which makes verification of taxonomy, state of preservation, and overall quality of the fossil record difficult. This makes the PBDB unsuitable for the intended purpose of documenting the fossil diversity at a specimen level. Besides that, we found several discrepancies and a limited number of turtle-yielding localities in PBDB compared to TED. PBDB provides less data compared to our prospection based on the literature and collection surveys. Such a result is logical, because PBDB deals with much broader scope in comparison to TED, which is much more limited in its taxonomic and geographic scope. As a result, we are in close relationship with PBDB community to mutually improve both datasets. A second option is the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the database mainly aimed at recording information on extant biodiversity. Whereas some fossil specimens are generally included in GBIF, the database does not allow inclusion and easy browsing of detailed information such as preservation or geological setting, which we consider to be relevant, nor it provides an easy and intuitive way of searching for individual specimens. Integrated Digitized Biocollections (iDigBio) is another possibility, seemingly fitting our needs and even having an associated team of people dealing with the fossils (iDigPaleo). Unfortunately, our tests revealed a set of limitations and suboptimal behaviors of the search engine (e.g., false positive hits based on partial fits of the taxonomic

names or specimen numbers, lack of distinguishing between original specimens and casts, false markings of geographic occurrences on the map based on the location of collection-holding institutions rather than sites of recovery, etc.) that would require far reaching changes to the search logic to make it usable for the purposes of our project. MorphoSource (MS) was the strongest contender for a specimen-level database of fossils and is the leading repository gathering 3D data of both extant and extinct vertebrates. Unfortunately, MS does not allow desirable Crossref Metadata Search, occurrence map, and has very limited search capabilities, disallowing temporal, geographic, or convenient taxonomic search at a supra-generic level. Because of that, its employment for our intended purpose necessitates a curated, taxonomically, temporarily, and geographically organized gateway. For that reason, while the TED is designed to integrate the benefits of MS, by linking to its resources, it also provides a more robust framework recording additional information and allowing more detailed search and browsing of records. Similarly to projects such as TEMNOS (Gee, 2024) or Portuguese Fossil Database (Fialho et al., 2023), we decided to create a new project and designed the webpage to fulfil our vision.

Methods

In Turtle Evolution Database (TED), we follow three different divisions of information with mutual linking: taxonomy, repositories, and reference database.

1. The taxonomic (Turtle specimens) search provides full collection numbers of specimens, their taxonomic allocation in the Family, Genus, and Species, their general status, nomenclature, preservation type, and a brief description. Geological and stratigraphic information includes the country of origin, general age, reference to exact numeric age (if available), locality, geological bed, member, formation, and basin. Finally, information about the repository, references, and additional information are provided. Visual content includes a general photo with the tax-

Fig. 1 Turtle-yielding localities in Czechia and Poland. AU, Austria; CZ, Czechia; DE, Germany; HU, Hungary; PL, Poland; SK, Slovakia

- onomic name, collection number, scale bar, and institutional and TED logos attached. Where relevant, links to MorphoSource are included.
- The Repositories division contains information about collections with their acronym, full name and address, and contact to the curator, who is responsible for the material and holding the copyright. All researchers are welcome to contact us or the curators directly to study the material in person.

- The Reference database is a simplified catalogue of included literature displayable both in an abbreviated and full format, with permitted downloadable PDFs.

Visual content

The photographs were mainly captured with Canon EOS M6 Mark II, and the attached figures were made using Corel PHOTO-PAINT and CorelDRAW software. 3D

models were produced with a Shining 3D EinScan Pro 2X 3D surface scanner fixed on a tripod with Ein-Turntable (alignment based on features), and EXScan Pro 3.2.0.2–3.7.0.3 software or photogrammetrically using Agisoft Metashape 2.2.0. All available models are uploaded to the MorphoSource project “[TED-Turtle Evolution Data-base, ID: 000693902](#)”. MorphoSource objects contain the same information as provided by the TED.

Use of data

TED showcases specimens housed and belonging to various repositories identified in the specimen records. Text information and media within TED are generally available under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC) license, allowing for broad sharing and use. 3D models shared through MorphoSource are available with individual copyright details for each specimen, by default with the In Copyright–Educational Use Permitted license. Other media within TED are protected by copyright and accessing them or sharing requires permissions from the housing repository which holds the copyright. The text information within TED is freely accessible.

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Data export

To share our data with other online platforms like GBIF, we follow the Darwin Core (Wieczorek et al., 2012). The information can be exported following international data standards for further research and improved interoperability among diverse data sources. To correctly synthesise the dataset, we follow the terms of the Darwin

Core Quick Reference Guide (<https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/>).

Contribution, further progress, and sustainability

We have created a straightforward online form for contributors to submit the required information and images regarding new turtle specimens. Our collaborative efforts aim to ensure the successful addition of new records. The database management and development is financially secured for the next 5 years, with a commitment to maintain the service for at least 10 years, as required by the grant program regulations. Necessary funding allowing perpetual function of the database will be periodically applied for in the form of grant applications to Czech and/or Polish funding institutions. All data deposited in the database will be backed up and, in case of the unlikely event of its discontinuation, raw records will be made publicly available in a form deemed the best for their preservation and accessibility at the time (e.g., an electronic supplement to a paper in a paleontology-focused scientific journal, a downloadable archive published on the institutional website and/or in Internet Archive, etc.). In the case of the cessation of the maintenance of the project, we are in close relation with PBDB community to share and therefore secure data from potential loss.

Conclusion

Turtle Evolution Database (TED) is a new online database of fossil turtles from Czechia and Poland, featuring detailed images and 3D models. In the spirit of Open Science, TED has enhanced global collaboration and accessibility to lesser-known collections. Researchers worldwide are encouraged to contribute, provide feedback, and collaborate to further the understanding of turtle evolution. The database is available under the link <https://ted.paleo.pan.pl/>.

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Author contributions

Both authors reviewed the historical literature, prepared the figure and the table and reviewed the manuscript.

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Data availability

TED showcases specimens housed and belonging to various repositories identified in the specimen records. Text information and media within TED are generally available under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC) license, allowing for broad sharing and use. 3D models shared through MorphoSource are available with individual copyright details for each specimen, by default with the In Copyright–Educational Use Permitted license. Other media within TED are protected by copyright and accessing them or sharing requires permissions from the housing repository, which holds the copyright. The text information within TED is freely accessible.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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